

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF WAVINESS-DOMINATED CONTROLLED MORPHOLOGY ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBE POLYMER COMPOSITES: MODELING STUDY CORRELATED WITH EXPERIMENTS

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1 Introduction

The elastic response of controlled-morphology nanocomposites comprised of aligned, but wavy, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) is studied theoretically and in comparison to prior experimental data. As opposed to filler-like concepts in the literature, aligned CNTs in this study have a morphology similar to fibers in advanced composites; aligned, high volume fraction (exceeding 20%), collimated, continuous, high graphitic quality and homogeneously dispersed in a surrounding matrix without voids or inclusions. Controlling and quantifying the morphology of CNTs is critical in determining the structure-property relations for nanocomposites. Aligned polymer nanocomposites (A-PNCs) are fabricated using capillary-driven wetting, avoiding dispersion issues and then mechanically densified [1] to obtain desired volume fractions so that the CNTs can dominate composite properties. Particularly important is the continuous nature of the CNTs across the sample, reaching lengths of ~2 mm. Waviness of the CNT reinforcement in the polymeric composites is shown to dominate the elastic response including the observation that tensile and compressive modulus show different behavior. An analytical reduction is utilized which allows the wavy CNT reinforcement to be straightforwardly implemented in finite element analyses; the strong dependence on CNT diameter that controls the amount of bending vs. extension contribution to composite modulus is deduced.

2. Experimental Study

A-PNCs are fabricated using capillarity-driven wetting [1], avoiding dispersion issues and then mechanically densified [2] up to ~20% volume fraction so that the CNTs can dominate composite

properties. Several techniques are used to characterize their morphology such as alignment, dispersion, voids, and the effect of the closely-packed CNTs on polymer curing. Figure 1 contains an exemplary morphological characterization of A-PNCs by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). CNT alignment preserved through the densification and compositing processes. Mechanical properties were investigated by nanoindentation technique due to small sizes of the PNC samples.

Figure 1. Controlled morphology polymer nanocomposites [2] (a) Image of 1% aligned CNT forest, 1% A-PNCs and pure epoxy (b) SEM image of 1% A-PNC (scalebar is 2 μ m) with an inset schematic of the CNT alignment direction .

Overall, the A-PNC properties show a volumetric effect from the CNTs in the modulus data. A linear trend in modulus is observed in Figure 2 with increasing volume fraction of A-PNCs from

the baseline epoxy for axial direction, a trend consistent with standard composite mechanics predictions such as simple rule of mixtures or Mori–Tanaka.

Figure 2. Indentation modulus of A-PNCs in axial direction with spherical indenter.

On the contrary, in the transverse direction, increasing the volume fraction does not give a linear increase in indentation modulus (see Figure 3). Besides different directions (axial and transverse), spherical type indentation was investigated as well. Spherical indentation remains in elastic region so that the modulus results of A-PNCs remain in the lower bound. Berkovich indentation data shows slightly higher results for modulus with the same trends.

Figure 3. Indentation modulus of A-PNCs in transverse direction with spherical indenter.

CNT waviness is noted as a dominant morphological effect controlling modulus by comparing the experimental results to standard composite theories modified to account for CNT waviness [2]

3. Modeling Study

Several models are used to investigate the reinforcing effects of CNTs in polymer composites including atomistic, molecular simulations. However incorporation of these simulations of CNTs to composites is tedious so micromechanical continuum approaches are more commonly used with better efficiency. Such models typically assume a perfect bonding of CNT to matrix with unrealistic geometries (such as solid, straight cylinders) without considering the waviness or bending effects of CNTs. Recently a few studies have taken waviness into account [3-5] with several assumptions that can be improved: appropriate elastic modulus assumptions, proper CNT geometry and bending of the CNT are not considered due to symmetric boundary conditions invoked. In the current work, an improved FE model is developed to understand the importance of those parameters. An analytical reduction is used (based on [3-5]) which allows the wavy CNT reinforcement to be straightforwardly implemented in finite element analyses.

3.1. Finite Element Analysis

To determine the effective reinforcing modulus (E_{RVE}) of an embedded wavy nanotube, a finite element analysis was developed with commercial software ANSYS. A representative volume element (RVE) was created having a single wavy nanotube with finite length CNT. The wavy CNT in polymer matrix can be characterized by a waviness ratio, w , of $w=a/L$ where a is the amplitude and L is the wavelength of a sinusoid. Three orthogonal planes of RVE are applied to symmetry boundary conditions of without shear and normal displacement. An axial displacement, δ , in the z direction is applied to form a strain with $\epsilon = \delta/L$, and a reaction force, F_t , was used to define a RVE modulus E_{RVE} :

$$E_{RVE} = \frac{F_t L}{A \delta}$$

In the preliminary analysis, a single walled CNT (SWNT) with an outer diameter of 2 nm and wall thickness of 0.075 nm and a wall modulus of 5TPa is considered. Several different approaches in the literature exists with different wall thickness and modulus pairs. However, a consistent analysis by Boyce et al. [6] will be used as a reference. With this proper CNT geometry and properties, a consistent axial (EA) and bending (EI) stiffnesses can be generated for the CNT in the finite element analysis. Figure 4 shows how RVE modulus of polymer nanocomposite modulus (E_{RVE}) is affected by increasing waviness ratio with inset schematics showing the wavy RVE. A matrix with a 1 GPa is considered with the volume fraction of polymer nanocomposite of $< 0.05\%$ so that RVE is wide enough to avoid boundary effects.

Figure 4. Reinforcing modulus of a wavy CNT embedded in a matrix, E_{RVE} with an increasing waviness ratio. Inset: Schematics of a wavy CNT embedded in a matrix.

3.2 Modeling Results and Discussion

The wavy nature of the CNTs has been investigated for four different waviness ratios showing a decrease in resulting reinforcing modulus from 1.041 GPa to 1.009 GPa. The results are in agreement with prior predictions from literature [3]. During the analysis both small and large deflection (SDA and LDA) studies have been performed.

Waviness of the CNT reinforcement in the polymeric composites is shown to dominate the elastic response including both for compressive and tensile modulus with a trend differences as shown in Figure 5. The contributions of total strain energy

have also been decomposed to bending and extension portions to observe the changes with waviness ratio variation. Since our A-PNCs studied experimentally have a waviness ratio of $w=0.185$ [2], the compression and tension behavior is investigated for waviness ratio of 0.15 and 0.2 to capture experimental waviness ratio. The analyses were performed from low (40 μ strain) to high (20,000 μ strain). The increasing strain ratio gives an increase in compressive modulus whereas for tensile modulus a decrease is observed. The CNT wavy nature is observed to have a better reinforcing capability in compressive than in tensile loading conditions.

Figure 5. Compressive and tensile modulus of RVE with an increasing strain for $w=0.15$ and $w=0.20$.

The different trends compressive and tensile loadings were not observed in the small deflection analyses.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, SWNT wavy CNT embedded in a polymer matrix is modeled with a proper CNT geometry and properties to capture realistic bending and extensional stiffness. The decrease in RVE modulus is in agreement with literature findings with increasing waviness ratio. The compressive and tensile modulus is also studied to investigate the different behaviors of the RVE. Waviness ratio of 0.15 and 0.20 is chosen to capture the experimental waviness ratio of A-PNCs studied earlier. The compressive modulus shows a linear increase with high strains whereas, tensile modulus shows a decrease. Future work includes understanding the mechanistic origins of the different tensile and

compressive trends in modulus with strain, and experimental-modeling correlations.

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